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**THEORIZING ABOUT LITERARY TRANSLATION: AN ENDURING
COGNITIVE PROCESS**

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada publitsistika va adabiyot nazariyasi, jahon adabiyoti durdonalarining hayotga tatbiqi, jamiyatga ta’siri ilmiy-nazariy jihatdan asoslab berilgan. O‘tmish va zamonaviy publitsistika aniq faktlar, ma’lumotlar asosida qiyosiy o‘rganilgan.

Аннотация: В настоящей статье речь идет о теории журналистики и теории литературы, обосновано практическое воплощение и влияние шедевров мировой литературы на общество. На основе фактологических сведений в сравнительном ракурсе изучаются историческая и современная публицистика.

Abstract: This article deals with modern theoretical journalism and literary theory, the practical application of masterpieces of world literature, and the needs of society.

History and modern journalism are compared. The necessary facts and information are studied separately.

Historically speaking, most translation theories have begun and developed either during or after the completion of specific translations of important literary works. Various difficult decisions that translators had to make on their respective works encouraged them to explain the reasoning behind their conclusion by writing an introduction, an afterword or larger projects on the topic at a later time. Occasionally their ideas were unconventional and generated many questions. Many such central questions concerning the state of the history of translation theories can be found in Hugo Friedrich’s article “On the Art of Translation.” This article defines some of the most important ideas that have had an impact on the development of translation theories starting from Ennius, Cicero, and Saint Jerome to Schleiermacher and Humboldt.

While Friedrich considers Ennius' translations from the Greek into Latin “acts of submission that caused awkward lexical Graecisms to enter into the translations,” he explains that later the translation from the Greek to Latin became an “appropriation of the original without any real concern for the stylistic and linguistic idiosyncrasies of the original.” He describes the works of both Cicero and Saint Jerome as some of the most important comments on to initiate the discussion about the theories of translation. As different translation approaches took place after the Roman period, where the goal was to enrich and develop new expressions “in one's own language,” he refers to

Quintilian and Pliny as representatives of the Renaissance theories where the “most striking hallmark is its effort to ‘enrich’ (enruhir; arricchire, aumentar)” the target language. Emphasis on stylistic characteristics, according to Friedrich, didn’t occur until the tradition of Seneca's language was ignored in pursuit of adapting to the new writing styles of

French writers, including Malherbe, Rabelais, Bonaventure des Periers, and Montaigne: “This form of writing took root as the result of a translation in which the translator felt free not only to appropriate the content of the original texts but also to create a style in opposition to that in the source language.” Nevertheless, it was a short-lived approach. In the mid eighteenth century the attention of the translators shifted toward the direction of a linguistic parallelism that was new and refreshing, especially in terms of a cultural consideration of both the source and the target languages. In Friedrich’s words, a “totally new type of translation and of translation theory emerged that ran parallel to the increasing tolerance of cultural differences. It was necessary to reduce the artistic, intellectual, or any other rivalry between languages and give equal standing to all languages.” Yet, in the eighteenth century, we see a different kind of parallelism: as the number of literary translators gradually increased, the ideas of what one should really accept as a sufficient translation increased simultaneously.

The conclusion, of course, was less than ideal and somewhat pessimistic. As Friedrich described it, there was “no such thing as an adequate translation; at best, one can hope for some tentative approximation”. Interestingly enough, it is not until the end of the essay that we can clearly see Friedrich’s own views on the topic. As he credits Schleiermacher and Humboldt for their role in developing a new approach to translation that resulted in a respect for the foreign language, he ends the first part of his essay with these thoughts:

The demands that Schleiermacher and Humboldt make can no longer be omitted from any subsequent theories of the art of translation. Yet current practitioners of translation rarely follow these theories. This is especially true for translators who are themselves distinguished writers. Often writer-translators practice the opposite mistake: instead of maintaining the style of the original, they elevate it. And if we follow the premise that all power comes from the original, then we must also accept the notion that the stylistic features of the translation should conform to those of the original, even when the original text is written in an ordinary or lower-class style.

More to the point, a glimpse into historical aspects of translation can familiarize us with some of the suggested qualities that a literary translator should have. This holds historical significance because who is and who can be a literary translator is a thought that was initiated as far back as in John Dryden’s time. To Dryden, the art of translation was a “disease” that can infect anyone, but to turn that act into a translation worth reading, one should not only be “a nice critic in his mother-tongue before he attempts to translate a foreign language” but also should have some prerequisite qualifications in order to deserve the attention of his or her audience. Dryden asserts that “the

qualification of a translator worth reading must be a mastery of the language he translates out of, and that he translates into; but if a deficiency to be allowed in either, it is in the original, since if he be but master enough of the tongue of his author as to be master of his sense, it is possible for him to express that sense with eloquence in his own, if he has a thorough command of that.” In his view, at that time there were only few works of translation that could have been considered as “tolerable,” and the reason he gives for that is “because there are so few who have all the talents which are requisite for translation, and that there is so little praise and so small encouragement for so considerable a part of learning...” He says this, of course, prompted by his high expectations of what a literary translation should be. In his theory, “translation is a kind of drawing after the life; where everyone will acknowledge there is a double sort of likeness, a good one and a bad.” And he is not alone in his requirements of learning continuity for translators. Karl Wilhelm Friedrich embraces Dryden’s ideas by expressing interest in creating a literary scholarship circle that would attract the membership of various artists and highly educated people. Later, Matthew Arnold deliberated along these lines as well. He saw scholarship as a positive step that would contribute on the betterment of the state the translation as a whole and insisted on the idea that translators should “try to satisfy scholars, because scholars alone have the means of really judging him.” He recognized the possibility that “a scholar may be a pedant,” which would mean “his judgment will be worthless” but he also hoped that “a scholar may also have poetical feeling, and then he can judge him truly; whereas all the poetical feeling in the world will not enable a man who is not a scholar to judge him truly.”

Speaking of difficulties and unique circumstances, I do realize that there are many more translation theories of the past and present (and many more which are still considered to be in their embryonic stage, including digital sound, nonverbal body language, and facial expressions) that I have not mentioned here. Nevertheless, the provided overall view, I hope, explains how the realistic power of language throughout the three to four millenniums has placed translators at the circumference of a deep sense of uncertainty and how that has shaped some of the translation theories discussed here. Since uncertainty is an integral part of the art and craft of translation, we can then conclude that the discussion of translation questions and translation theories will never end for as long as cross-cultural communication is necessary.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Adams, Robert M. *Proteus: His Lies, His Truth: Discussions of Literary Translation*. New York: W. W. Norton, 1973.
2. Amos, Flora Ross. *Early Theories of Translation*. New York: Columbia University Press, 1920.
3. Arrowsmith, William and Shattuck, Roger, editors. *The Craft and Context of Translation*. Austin: University of Texas Press, 1961.
4. Baker, Mona. *Routledge Encyclopedia of Translation Studies*. 1998
Barnstone, Willis. *The Poetics of Translation-History, Theory, Practice*. New Haven, Connecticut. Yale University Press. 1993.
5. Barnstone, Willis. "ABC's of Translation" in *Translation Review* 2: 35-36. 1978.
6. Bassnett, Susan. *Translation Studies*. Rev. ed. Ed. Terence Hawkes. New York: Routledge, 1991.
7. Beaugrande, Robert de. *Factors in a Theory of Poetic Translating*. Amsterdam: Van Gorcum, 1978.
8. Bellitt, Ben. *Adam's Dream: A Preface to Translation*. New York: Grove Press, 1978.
9. Biguenet, John and Rainer Schulte, editors. *The Craft of Translation*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1989.
10. Brower, Reuben A., editor. *On Translation*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1959.
11. Davie, Donald. *Poetry in Translation*. Walton Hall, Milton Keynes: The Open University Press, 1975.